

Water Pretreatment System for Rapid Preconcentration of Bacteria

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Abstract—Water is a finite precious resource, and waterborne bacterial and viral diseases are a prominent health risk to humans and animals that needs to be urgently addressed. To protect public health, water management authorities and water-treatment facilities must monitor both the source and the treated water, where pathogens contaminants are generally present at low concentrations. Rapid quantification methods are needed, combining concentration processes and very sensitive detection systems. Because the numbers of these microorganisms are often quite low, large volumes of water are usually needed to be processed for accessing water preconcentration before the detection. However, efficient pretreatment of large water volumes at the source, is a pressing problem for water resource management and in-line continuous monitoring.

This study aims to offer a retreatment methodology to this pressing water quality monitoring problem, with the key objective of advancing water sampling enrichment methodologies to rapidly and efficiently preconcentrate viruses and bacteria in-line in the water chain for timely preventing outbreaks. The proposed methodology and prototype system target fast realization of water analysis pretreatment steps, avoiding the use of separate, time-consuming, and manual laboratory procedures. The presented prototype system uses highly efficient and low-cost Monolithic Adsorption Filters (MAF) for the preconcentration of *E.coli* bacterium. A recovery percentage of 63% is reported for feeded *E.coli* concentration at 10^6 cells/10 L.

Keywords— Bacteria, Crossflow Ultrafiltration (CUF), Monolithic Adsorption Filters (MAF), Water Preconcentration

I. INTRODUCTION

CURRENTLY all methods used for the detection of viruses and bacteria in water are laboratory-based [1]. Methods for detection of pathogens are applied for many years in medical diagnosis; some of these methods were modified to be utilized in analysis of environmental samples and most of them need DNA extraction as an intermediate step for the detection analysis (e.g. quantitative Polymerase Chain-Reaction -qPCR, Nucleic Acid Amplification Tests -NAAT). However, concentration levels of viruses and bacteria in environmental waters are often below the limit of detection (LOD) of standard analysis (e.g. qPCR). Rapid quantification methods are needed combining concentration processes [2] and very sensitive detection systems [3]. Thus,

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preconcentration steps are needed for acquiring sample enrichment [4]. The major requirements of preconcentration methods are (I) easy implementation, preferably compatible with field application, (II) large volumes of water sample handling, (III) short processing times, (IV) affordable costs, (V) reproducibility and high recovery rates.

The most common applied methods for virus concentration from water are based on the principle of adsorption and elution. A solid matrix is used to adsorb microorganisms while the water is removed and then is eluted in a smaller volume. Thereby, pathogenic microorganisms' concentration is increased, which in turn decreases the LOD. Adsorption and elution are based on electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions between the solid matrix and the microorganisms. Their strength depends mainly on the net surface charge of the microorganisms and can be controlled by pH and ionic strength conditions. Most viruses are negatively charged in water, whereas matrices for adsorption can either be positively or negatively charged. Positively charged matrices such as Nano-Ceram filters® have the benefit that they allow for direct interaction with viruses but are commonly expensive [5]. More economical solutions represent negatively charged filters [6] or skimmed milk flocculation (SMF) [7]. However, they require pre-conditioning of water samples by adjusting pH or ionic strength conditions to enable virus adsorption, which furthermore restricts their application in field studies. Another inexpensive approach is glass wool filtration, which allows for a direct adsorption of pathogens. Nonetheless, its recovery efficiency is known to have strong variances [8]. A solution to overcome the disadvantages of existing methods was introduced by applying monolithic adsorption filtration (MAF) for enrichment of bacteriophages from water at neutral pH [9] and is also applied for bacteria [10]. The method uses macroporous monoliths as a solid matrix for adsorption. The production of these monoliths is inexpensive, while their electrical surface charge can be tailored by chemical modification [11], hereby, can be customized and adapted to the required enrichment conditions for the targeted microorganisms. Also, MAF displays a rapid and affordable tool for concentrating pathogens with high flow rates of up to 1L/min [12].

The following study presents a preconcentration prototype system that uses two-stage filtration subsystems, i) a crossflow ultrafiltration (CUF) and ii) a monolithic adsorption filtration with MAFs filters, for the preconcentration of *E.coli* bacteria.

II. THE INTEGRATED PRECONCENTRATION SYSTEM

Fig. 1 presents the integrated preconcentration prototype system, which can execute automatically the enrichment of bacteria from large water volumes of 10 L. The following subsections present separately the two-filtration processes

used by the preconcentrator, which are i) a CUF filtration at the left-hand side of the system, and ii) a MAF filtration at the right-hand side of the system, which is equipped with an automated filter exchange mechanism for the MAF filters.

Fig. 1 The preconcentration prototype system.

A. Crossflow Ultrafiltration (CUF) Subsystem

The CUF subsystem executes crossflow ultrafiltration (CUF) to enrich rapidly microorganisms in treated wastewater (TWW) or in any other type of water sample (e.g. tap water). In the first step, a water sample is concentrated by CUF depending on size, via a dialysis membrane from Fresenius (FX-80, 1.8 m² membrane area). The TWW sample is separated into filtrate water and concentrated microorganisms, which are held back by CUF. The concentrate stream is recirculated in a loop using a peristaltic pump (PP1). As shown in Fig. 2, the filtration process is controlled by six solenoid pinch valves: the sample valve (V8), the recirculation valve (V1) and the elution valve (V3), as well as the deaeration valve (V2), and for the cleaning procedure the sterilized-water valve (V9) and the NaOCl- valve (V10). Transmembrane pressure is measured using three pressure sensors located at the FX-80 filter's inlet (Pin), outlet (Pout) and filtrate side (Pfilter). Transmembrane pressure can be adjusted via a Restriction Valve. The filtration flow is measured by a flow sensor.

Fig. 2 Crossflow ultrafiltration schematic representation.

The individual components are controlled by a custom LabView software GUI (Fig. 3) that can be launched via a

LabView executable. This GUI can be used for the manual, but also for the automated control of the instrument. Specifically, the GUI includes a) push buttons for opening and closing the solenoid valves, b) push buttons for controlling the peristaltic pump and its rotation site, c) indicators for three pressure sensors, d) indicators for the flow rate, the filtrated sample in liters, and the transmembrane pressure (TMP), e) graphical representation of the flow rate and TMP, f) two cursors for setting different parameters such as the liters and the chlorine time, and g) several push buttons for the execution of the different preconcentration procedures such as deaeration, concentration, elution and cleaning.

Fig. 3 GUI for CUF process.

B. Monolithic Adsorption Filtration (MAF) Subsystem

The MAF subsystem executes crossflow monolithic adsorption filtration (cMAF) to enrich microorganisms in any type of water sample. In the cMAF subsystem the flow of the water is executed tangentially over the MAF disc, and this allows the capturing of microorganisms mainly on the surface of the MAF avoiding its blocking at the same time. This configuration allows larger sample volume (with high turbidity) and high flow rates for the sample collection. Around 100mL-10L water sample is concentrated by cMAF, where the sample is separated into filtrate (waste) water and concentrated microorganisms which are held back by MAF. The concentrate stream is recirculated in a loop using a peristaltic pump (PP2). Based on Fig. 4, the filtration process is controlled by four solenoid pinch valves: the sample valve (V4), the recirculation valve (V6) and the elution valve (V7), as well as the waste valve (V5). After the MAF process, a concentrate sample is obtained on the MAF surface, which is eluted with an elution buffer, pumped via a syringe pump.

Fig. 4 Crossflow MAF filtration schematic representation.

The MAF subsystem is controlled via a LabView-based GUI (Fig. 5), as well, in a manual and an automatic manner. Specifically, all the parts such as the valves, the pumps and the MAF exchange mechanism are controlled manually via push buttons. On the other hand, for the automatic control of the different filtration procedures, such as MAF adsorption, MAF elution, cleaning, there are dedicated push buttons.

Fig. 5 GUI for MAF process.

III. VALIDATION OF THE PRECONCENTRATION SYSTEM

For the validation of the preconcentration system performance, initial samples of different concentrations of *E.coli*, 10^5 cells/ml, 10^6 cells/ml, 10^7 cells/ml, were used. The initial samples were added into 10 L of water for creating *E. coli* concentrations of 10^5 cells/10 L, 10^6 cells/10 L, 10^7 cells/10 L respectively. After running the ‘concentration procedure’ of the 10 L water, the 1 ml concentrated sample was collected and compared with the initial sample for calculating the bacteria-recovery ratio that the system can achieve. The counting of the bacteria in the initial sample (Feed sample) and in the output sample (Eluate sample) was realized by using ‘Thoma Cell’ counting. The concentration analysis was repeated three times for each concentration in order to estimate the standard deviation. At the same time, the ‘cleaning procedure’ was validated during each concentration analysis. The ‘cleaning procedure’ uses a) NaOCl to kill any bacteria left into the system and b) distilled water to clean the tubes/parts from any NaOCl. Therefore, two things needed to be verified, a) if any chlorine and b) if any bacteria have been left over into the system, after running the ‘cleaning procedure’. Both situations affect the next analysis in the following manner: a) the existence of high concentration of Chlorine would kill the bacteria of the next analysis and b) the existence of bacteria from the last analysis will give inaccurate results for the next analysis. The validation for the existence of any bacteria after the cleaning was made by incubating samples extracted from two parts of the module, a) from the CUF output and b) the MAF output. Simultaneously, a chlorine test kit that uses colorimetric, DPD method with colour-disk comparator, was used for measuring the chlorine concentration at these two samples. All runs have shown

sufficient removal of the chlorine, with concentrations below 0.25 mg/L and sometimes zero or almost zero mg/L. All the runs have shown sufficient cleaning of the bacteria, as well. These tests use the experimental setup in Fig. 6 that includes the preconcentration system with all the substances (NaOCl, distilled water, buffer,) and materials (CUF filter, MAF filters, sample tubes) needed for running a concentration analysis.

Fig. 6 Experimental setup of the preconcentration system.

Fig. 7 shows the average result of the Eluate concentrations at different Feed concentrations, (1) 10^5 cells/10 L, (2) 10^6 cells/10 L and (3) 10^7 cells/10 L, and Fig. 8 demonstrates the recovery ratios, 62.1%, 63.2%, 35% respectively, for the three different Feed concentrations.

Fig. 7 Comparison of the Feed and Eluate concentrations.

Fig. 8 Recovery percentage at different Feed concentrations,

(1) 10^5 , (2) 10^6 and (3) 10^7 cells/10L.

Fig. 9 shows the results in a different representation that better demonstrates the higher performance of the system at lower concentrations (10^5 cells/10 L) and its lower performance at higher feed concentrations (10^7 cells/10 L).

Fig. 9 Recovery experiments at different feed concentrations of E.coli. The data points are shown with standard deviations. Continuous line represents fictive recoveries of 100%). Both axes are logarithmic.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study successfully demonstrates a water pretreatment system designed for rapid preconcentration of bacteria, particularly *E. coli*, using a two-stage filtration approach combining Crossflow Ultrafiltration (CUF) and Monolithic Adsorption Filtration (MAF). The system enables efficient and automated water sample enrichment, achieving a recovery rate of up to 63% for bacterial concentrations at 10^6 cells/10 L. Validation tests confirm the system's effectiveness in bacterial concentration, as well as the efficiency of its cleaning procedure, ensuring no cross-contamination between analyses. This approach has significant potential for real-time water quality monitoring and early outbreak prevention.

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